

Job Satisfaction of Female Workers in Different Garments Factories in Dhaka City: An Intertemporal Comparison

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Abstract: Job satisfaction is an attitude that reflects the extent to which an individual is gratified by or fulfilled in his/her job. It is an affective or emotional response toward various facets of one's job. This meaning of job satisfaction implies that job satisfaction is not a unitary concept. Rather a person can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of his or her job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects. Thus, we can differentiate at least two aspects of job satisfaction — facet satisfaction and overall satisfaction. Facet satisfaction is the tendency for an employee to be more or less satisfied with various facets of his or her job. A large number of related research has been conducted in different countries including Bangladesh. Alam (1986) conducted a research on the job satisfaction of female workers in different garment factories in Dhaka City in 1983. He measured the level of overall satisfaction and analyzed the nature of facet satisfaction of 200 female workers. He concluded that a minor percentage of female workers in different garment factories are satisfied with their jobs, and there is a positive relationship between their level of job satisfaction and the level of wages/salaries and other identified factors. The objective of the present study is to measure the overall level of job satisfaction of female workers in different garment factories and to identify factors contributing to job satisfaction and factors contributing to job dissatisfaction. The present study also ranks all identified factors according to their relative importance by using a formula developed by Alam in 1983 (Alam, 1986). Finally, the present study makes intertemporal comparisons of overall job satisfaction level and of the nature of facet satisfaction over the twenty two-year period (between 1983 and 2005). Such intertemporal comparisons are necessary because of the fact that over the last twenty two years, as the garment industries of the country has expanded significantly, the nature of human resource management in this sector has changed in many aspects. As a result, job satisfaction status and the absolute as well as relative importance of factors contributing to satisfaction level are expected to change.

1. Introduction and Related Research

Job satisfaction is an attitude that reflects the extent to which an individual is gratified by or fulfilled in his/her job. In simple words, job satisfaction essentially reflects the extent to which an individual likes his or her job. Formally defined, job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response toward various facets of one's job. This definition implies that job satisfaction is not a unitary concept. Rather a person can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of his or her job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects. Thus, we can differentiate at least two aspects of job satisfaction — facet satisfaction and overall satisfaction. Facet satisfaction is the tendency for an employee to be more or less satisfied with various facets of his or her job. Some of these important facets are: the work itself, salary, promotions, recognition, the work itself, working conditions, job security, supervision, and co-workers. On the other hand, an overall satisfaction is an overall, or summary, indicator of a person's attitude toward his or her job that cuts across the various facets. In a sense, overall satisfaction is an average or total of the attitudes individuals hold toward various facets of the job. Thus, two workers might express the same level of overall satisfaction for different reasons. Specifically, they would have offsetting attitudes toward various facets of the job.

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A large number of related research have been conducted in different countries including Bangladesh. Job satisfaction is one of the most frequently studied work attitudes by Organizational Behavior researchers. For example, more than 12,000 job satisfaction studies were published by the early 1990s (Naughton, 2001). However, an important foundational theory of work motivation which identified the factors contributing to job satisfaction is the Dual-Structure Theory of Frederick Herzberg *et al* in the late 1950s and early 1960s Herzberg *et al*, 1959, Herzberg, 1968). Job satisfaction had up until then been viewed as a single-structure construct, ranging from satisfaction to dissatisfaction. Herzberg *et al* concluded that the traditional model of job satisfaction and motivation was incorrect. They reasoned, a single set of factors should influence movement back and forth along the continuum. But the research of Herzberg *et al*, had identified differential influences from two different sets of factors, they argued that two different dimensions must be involved. Thus, job satisfaction and work motivation were seen as dual-structure phenomena. There is one dimension ranging from satisfaction to no satisfaction and another ranging from dissatisfaction to no dissatisfaction. Presumably the two dimensions must be associated with the two sets of factors identified by Herzberg *et al*. Thus, this theory proposed that employees might be either satisfied or not satisfied and, at the same time, dissatisfied or not dissatisfied. According to this theory, there are two sets of factors — motivation factors (or intrinsic factors) and hygiene factors (or extrinsic factors). Motivation factors are achievement, recognition, the work itself, responsibility, and advancement and growth. When present in a job, these motivation factors apparently can cause satisfaction and motivation; when they are absent, the result is feelings of no satisfaction (as opposed to dissatisfaction). On the other hand, Hygiene factors are supervision, working conditions, interpersonal relationships, pay, job security, and company policy and administration. When the hygiene factors are seen as inadequate, feelings of dissatisfaction may arise. When these factors are considered acceptable, an employee is not dissatisfied (but not necessarily satisfied).

Subsequent to the study of Herzber *et al*, a considerable number of empirical studies designed to test the validity of this theory (also known as “The Two-Factor Theory”) were published, and a heated controversy has developed between supporters and critics of this theory. But in Bangladesh, so far few systematic analyses have been conducted to examine the state of job satisfaction among working women of this country and to investigate the factors contributing to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Chaudhury (1977) conducted a research related to these problems. His study was an attempt to examine, among other things, the state of job satisfaction among the non-agricultural working women of Bangladesh and to find out the reasons for dissatisfaction in their jobs. In his study, the overall job satisfaction of a working woman was determined in terms of the following: (i) whether she is happy with her present working conditions (level of wages/salaries, job security, the job itself, promotion, office environment, etc.) and does she feel that men get better treatment in terms of salary and promotion than women at her place of work? The respondents were taken for this study from different occupational groups of Dhaka City. The study estimated that 71% of the respondents were happy with their current jobs and the reasons for job dissatisfaction were low pay, low job security, the job itself, low chances of promotion, unhealthy office environment, and others. Out of these reasons, low pay was the most common reason (not necessarily the most important reason) for dissatisfaction. The study was conducted on the basis of a sample taken in 1974. Chaudhury attempted to find out the relationship of the level of job satisfaction to age, education, and type of job or profession.

Islam (1975) conducted a study in which she examined the state of job satisfaction among middle class female workers of Dhaka City in 1975. The findings of this study about the pattern of job satisfaction were similar to those in Chaudhury's study.

Another related research was conducted by Hussain (1958) on the basis of a sample of 1956. He found that 94% of a sample of middle class Muslim female workers in Dhaka City were satisfied in their current jobs.

Alam (1986) conducted a research on the job satisfaction of female workers in different garment factories in Dhaka City in 1983. He measured the level of overall satisfaction and analyzed the nature of facet satisfaction of 200 female workers. He concluded the following:

- i. A minor percentage of female workers in different garment factories are satisfied with their jobs.
- ii. There is a positive relationship between their level of job satisfaction and the level of wages/salaries.
- iii. Economic importance of the present job is the most important factor, whereas, absence of better/similar job opportunities is the second most important factor contributing to job satisfaction.
- iv. Low job security is the most important factor, whereas, low level of wages/salaries is the second most important factor contributing to dissatisfaction with jobs.

2. Objective of the Present Study

The first objective of this study is to measure the overall level of job satisfaction of female workers in different garment factories and to identify factors contributing to job satisfaction and factors contributing to job dissatisfaction. The study ranks all identified factors according to their relative importance by using a formula developed by the researcher in 1983 (Alam, 1986). The second objective of this study is to make intertemporal comparisons of overall job satisfaction level and of the nature of facet satisfaction over the last twenty two years (from 1983 to 2005).

3. Methodology

- (A). **Sample:** 200 female workers between 16 and 35 years of age, irrespective of marital and religious status, employed in operating jobs in 14 different garment factories situated in Dhaka City area were randomly chosen for the present study. Out of 200 respondents, 84 were married and the rest 116 were unmarried, divorcee, or separated. All respondents were employed in operating sewing machines and other similar operating jobs. Workers employed in ironing were not included.
- (B). **Instrument:** A structured questionnaire was employed to collect all necessary primary data. The respondents were personally questioned and the questionnaires were filled in by the interviewer based on the responses of the respondents.
- (C). The study ranks all identified factors according to their relative importance by using a formula developed by Alam in 1983 (Alam, 1986).

(D). Methods of Calculation of Relative Importance of the Factors Contributing to Job Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction developed by Alam in 1983: In computing mean scores of relative importance (MSRI) of the factors contributing to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction the following formula has been used:

$$MSRI = \frac{\sum W + (n - f)N}{n}$$

Where, $\sum W$ = Total sum of cardinal weights assigned to different degrees of importance for the factor in question pointed out by the respondents.

n = Total sample size (total number of respondents).

f = Total number of respondents pointed out the factor in question (the frequency of the factor).

N = Total number of factors contributing to job satisfaction (or dissatisfaction) pointed out by any of the respondents.

In calculating total cardinal weights, ordinal weights, such as 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and so on have been converted into cardinal weights as follows:

<u>Ordinal Weight</u>	<u>Cardinal Weight</u>
I (first)	1
II (second)	2
III (third)	3
IV (fourth)	4
V (fifth)	5
VI (sixth)	6
VII (seventh)	7
VIII (eighth)	8
IX (ninth)	9

This formula was developed by Alam in 1983 (Alam, 1983). It is important to mention that there is not any other method available to measure the relative importance of various factors that contribute to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction.

On the other hand, to measure the overall status of job satisfaction or dissatisfaction, expected discrepancy technique (sometimes known as “Met Expectation”) has been used. The Met Expectations represent the difference between what an individual expects to receive from his/her job (such as good pay, good working condition, etc.) and what s/he perceives s/he is actually receiving from his/her job. In other words, the overall level of job satisfaction is measured by the following formula:

$$\text{Level of Overall Job Satisfaction} = \left[\frac{\text{Expected value or utility from the job}}{\text{Perceived value received from the job}} \right] \times 100$$

If the value, for example, is 60, then the employee is 60% satisfied with his/her job. On the other hand, if the value is 100, then the employee is fully satisfied with his/her job at present. However, if the value exceeds 100, s/he is a **delighted employee**. It is important to mention that the expected utility or expected value from a job and the perceived utility or perceived value from that job varies from person to person. Even when two persons are getting same benefits from their jobs, they may evaluate their benefits differently. Thus providing identical benefits and other utilities to all employees does not mean that the perceived values received from the jobs are equal for all employees or all employees are equally satisfied, since their expectations from their jobs may vary.

There are two other methods of measuring overall job satisfaction: Job Descriptive Index (JDI and Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ). But both the methods are highly subjective and, according to these methods, the overall job satisfaction score depends on the judgment of the researcher regarding the relative weights or importance of some selective facets of a job. As a result, they have not been considered in this study.

4. The Causes of Job Satisfaction

Five predominant models of job satisfaction focus on different causes of job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. They are need fulfillment, discrepancy, value attainment, equity, and dispositional/genetic components.

- i. Need Fulfillment:** These models propose that job satisfaction is determined by the extent to which the characteristics of a job allow an individual to fulfill his or her needs. For example, a survey of 30 Massachusetts law firms revealed that 35% to 50% of law-firm associates left their employers within three years of starting because the firms did not accommodate family needs. This example illustrates that unmet needs can affect both job satisfaction and turnover (Erdman, 2001). Although these models generated a great degree of controversy, it is generally accepted that need fulfillment is correlated with job satisfaction.
- ii. Discrepancies:** These models propose that job satisfaction is a result of met expectations. Met expectations represent the difference between what an individual expects to receive from a job, such as good pay and promotional opportunities, and what he or she actually receives. When expectations are greater than what is received, a person will be dissatisfied. In contrast, this model predicts the individual will be satisfied when he or she attains outcomes above and beyond expectations. A meta-analysis of 31 studies that included 17,241 people demonstrated that met expectations were significantly related to job satisfaction (Goodman *et al.*, 1988).
- iii. Value Attainment:** The idea underlying value attainment is that job satisfaction results from the perception that a job allows for fulfillment of an individual's important work values. In general, research consistently supports the prediction that value fulfillment is positively related to job satisfaction (LeBlanc and Mulvey, 1998). Managers can thus enhance employee satisfaction by structuring the work environment and its associated rewards and recognition to reinforce employees' values.

- iv. **Equity:** In this model, job satisfaction is a function of how fairly an individual is treated at work. Satisfaction results from one's perception that work outcomes, relative to inputs, compare favorably with a significant other's outcome/inputs. A meta-analysis involving 190 studies and 64,757 people supported this model. Employees perceptions of being treated fairly at work were highly related to overall job satisfaction (Mitchell, 1994). Managers thus are encouraged to monitor employees' fairness perceptions and to interact with employees in such a way that they feel equitably treated.
- v. **Dispositional/Genetic Model:** This model is based on the belief that job satisfaction is partly a function of both personal traits and genetic factors. As such, this model implies that stable individual differences are just as important in explaining job satisfaction as are characteristics of the work environment. Although only a few studies have tested these propositions, results support a positive, significant relationship between personal traits and job satisfaction over time periods ranging from 2 to 50 years. Genetic factors also were found to significantly predict life satisfaction, well-being, and general job satisfaction. Overall, researchers estimate that 30% of an individual's job satisfaction is associated with dispositional and genetic components (DeGrandpre, 2000).

5. Analysis and Findings of the Study

Table 1 provides a frequency distribution of the respondents according to the overall levels of job satisfaction of 200 female workers of 14 different garments factories located in Dhaka City.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of 200 Female Workers According to the Levels of Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction Status	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Satisfied (Level of Satisfaction: 60% - 100%*)	82	41.0%
Moderately Satisfied/Moderately Dissatisfied or Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied (Level of Satisfaction: 40% - <60%)	71	35.5%
Dissatisfied (Level of Satisfaction: 0%* - < 40%)	47	23.5%
Total	200	100%

* No respondent was 100% or 0% satisfied. Maximum and minimum levels of satisfaction are 90% and 30%, respectively.

From the above Table, we find that out of 200 respondents, 82 respondents (that is, 41% respondents) were satisfied with their present jobs. In 1983, Alam (1986) found that 23% respondents were satisfied with their jobs. On the other hand, Table 1 shows that 35.5% of the respondents were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied which implies that they are moderately satisfied with their present jobs in 2005. Alam found that only 26% respondents were in this category in 1983. In 2005, the number of dissatisfied female workers were 23.5%, whereas in 1983, 51% female workers in garments factories were dissatisfied.

Over the last 22 years, the overall level of job satisfaction of the female workers of different garments factories has increased. This is due to the fact that, the garments factories are now more organized and manage their human resources more formally. In addition, the garment factories now need to comply with certain rules and regulations in managing their female workers. On the other hand, the present study found that attitude of management of garments factories are now more motivational and professional than exploitative. In 1983, attitude of management toward female workers in different garments factories was neither quite motivational nor professional. Such shift in management attitude has contributed to improve the job satisfaction levels of female workers in different garments factories. Thus the present study found that the relative importance of different factors contributing to job satisfaction as well as dissatisfaction has changed. In addition, some of the factors that were quite important in determining the overall level of job satisfaction 22 years ago are now no longer important at all. Let us now list the factors contributing to job satisfaction (and not to dissatisfaction) of female workers of different garments factories according to their relative importance vis-à-vis the same list in 1983 in the following Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: List of Factors Contributing to Job Satisfaction and Their Frequency Distribution in 2005 and in 1983*

SL.	Factor	Frequency (1983)		Frequency (2005)	
		No.	%	No.	%
1.	Pay	0	0%	200	100.0%
2.	Economic importance of the present job	200	100%	200	100.0%
3.	Absence of better alternative job	185	93%	122	61.0%
4.	The work itself	175	88%	75	37.5%
5.	Interpersonal relations with peers	60	30%	102	51.0%
6.	Achievement	45	23%	0	0%
7.	Possibility of growth	25	13%	0	0%
8.	Advancement	10	5%	0	0%
9.	Working environment/condition	0	0%	52	26.0%

* The determining question was "Tick out the factors contributing to your satisfaction with your present job from the list of following 10 factors---." The other factor was recognition.

From the above Table 2, we find that in 2005, five factors (pay which includes overtime and all other pecuniary benefits, absence of better alternative job, the work itself, interpersonal relations with peers, and working environment) have contributed to job satisfaction of female workers in different garment factories. Among these five factors, pay is the most common one, followed by absence of better alternative job. This implies that **need fulfillment** has become an important determinant of job satisfaction. On the other hand, since interpersonal relations with peers and the work itself also contribute to job satisfaction of female workers, it can be concluded that the workers find **value attainment** (except recognition) in their jobs. As mentioned earlier. The idea underlying **value attainment** is that job satisfaction results from the perception that a job allows for fulfillment of an individual's important work values.

In 1983, economic importance of the present job, achievement, possibility of growth, and advancement were among the factors that positively contributed to the job satisfaction of female workers of different garment factories. However, these factors have lost their importance in determining the level of job satisfaction of these female workers in 2005.

On the other hand, pay and working environment did not contribute to job satisfaction of female workers of different garment factories in 1983 (instead, we will soon find that these two factors contributed to job dissatisfaction in 1983). However, in 2005, pay has become the most common and most important factor contributing to job satisfaction of these female workers, and working environment has also become, though low in importance, a factor contributing to job satisfaction of female workers in different garment factories. This is perhaps due to the fact that compared to 1983, overall pay of these female workers has increased sufficiently enough to allow female workers to meet their basic need fulfillment. On the other hand, due to external pressure and other reasons, working environment has improved over the last 22 years and as a result of which working environment is contributing to job satisfaction.

Table 3 reports the mean score of relative importance of each of the factors contributing to job satisfaction of the female workers of garments factories (in 2005 and in 1983).

Table 3: Mean Score of Relative Importance (MSRI)* of Each Factor Contributing to Job Satisfaction (in 2005 and in 1983)**

SL.	Factor	MSRI in 1983	MSRI in 2005
1.	Pay	-	1.250
2.	Economic importance of the present job	1.175	1.900
3.	Absence of better alternative job	2.500	2.180
4.	The work itself	3.225	4.650
5.	Interpersonal relations with peers	6.050	3.250
6.	Achievement	6.175	-
7.	Possibility of growth	6.650	-
8.	Advancement	6.875	-
9.	Working vironment/condition	-	6.150

* The determining question was "...state the degree of relative importance of the factors at the right hand side of each factor contributing to your present job satisfaction.

** Lower MSRI represents higher degree of importance.

From Table 3, we find that in 1983, the most important factor contributing to job satisfaction of female workers of different garments factory was the economic importance of the present job. In 2005, this factor is second most important factor in 2005. Pay has become the most important factor in 2005. In 1983, the level of pay was low in the garments industries. Workers were unhappy with their pay. As a result, low pay was the second most important factor that contributed to job dissatisfaction in 1983. The change in the role of pay over the last 22 years is due to the fact

that jobs in garments factories have brought a sense of self-achievement among the female workers. Absence of better alternative job was third important factor in 2003, and in 2005, its relative important has not been changed.

Absence of better alternative job has become more important in absolute term, but has slid down from its second position to third position in 2005. That is, absence of better alternative job contributes to increase the overall job satisfaction of the female workers. On the other hand, the relative importance of the work itself has remained more or less same over the last 22 years. However, “interpersonal relations with peers” has remained the fifth most important factor contributing to job satisfaction. Over the last 22 years, this factor has become more common (see Table 2) and its absolute importance has also increased significantly.

Table 4 lists the factors along with their frequencies that contributed to job dissatisfaction of female garments workers in 1983 and 2005.

Table 4: List of Factors Contributing to Job Dissatisfaction and Their Frequency Distribution in 2005 and in 1983*

SL	Factor	Frequency (1983)		Frequency (2005)	
		No.	%	No.	%
1.	Low job security	190	95%	200	100%
2.	Low level of wages/salaries	150	75%	72	36.0%
3.	Family life	95	47%	15	7.5%
4.	Company policy and administration	91	45%	149	74.5%
5.	No chance of advancement	75	37%	70	35.0%
6.	Absence of recognition	66	23%	126	63.0%
7.	No possibility of growth	54	27%	12	6.0%
8.	Working environment/condition	34	17%	66	33.0%

* The determining question was “Tick out the factors contributing to your dissatisfaction with your present job from the list of following 7 factors. Add any other factor (s) if you find relevant”

From Table 4 we find that low job security was most common factor that contributed to job dissatisfaction of female workers of different garments factories in 1983. Over the last 22 years, low job security remained as the most common factor for job dissatisfaction. Female workers of different garments factories suffer from severe job insecurity and their attitudes (which are a product of beliefs and values) toward their jobs are that they feel that they may lose their jobs at any time without any reason. Job insecurity not only reduces job satisfaction but also motivates workers not to work sincerely that in turn reduces the productivity of the employees.

On the other hand, in 1983, low level of pay was a very important factor that reduces job satisfaction of female workers in different garments factories. However, compared to 1983, total pay including overtime was not very low in 2005. As a result, only 36% respondents have complained about it. However, this does not mean that the level of pay has lost its importance in determining the level of job dissatisfaction, since frequency represents commonality and not the relative importance.

From Table 4, we also find that in 1983 family life was common factor that reduces job satisfaction of female workers of different garments factories. However, in 2005, family life has become a less common factor in determining job dissatisfaction. This is perhaps due to the fact that “families” have adjusted to the jobs of these female workers over time. As a result, in 2005, only 7.5% respondents have identified family life as a factor contributing to their job dissatisfaction, while in 1983, 47% respondents complained about family life contributing to their job dissatisfaction.

On the other hand, “working environment/condition” has remained a factor that causes job dissatisfaction of female workers. However, over the last twenty years, it has become a more common factor. In 1983, only 17% respondents identified it as a factor contributing to job dissatisfaction. In 2005, 33% respondents have identified it as a factor that contributes to dissatisfaction of female workers with their jobs.

Table 5 reports the MSRI of the factors contributing to job dissatisfaction in jobs in 1983 and in 2005.

Table 5: Mean score of Relative Importance (MSRI)* of Each Factor Contributing to Job Dissatisfaction (in 2005 and in 1983)**

SL.	Factor	MSRI in 1983	MSRI in 2005
1.	Low job security	1.320	1.850
2.	Low level of wages/salaries	3.110	4.265
3.	Family life	5.275	6.910
4.	Company policy and administration	5.830	2.312
5.	No chance of advancement	6.125	5.225
6.	Absence of recognition	6.410	3.956
7.	No possibility of growth	6.845	7.120
8.	Working environment/condition	7.220	4.8556

* The determining question was “...state the degree of relative importance of the factors at the right hand side of each factor contributing to dissatisfaction in your present job.

** Lower MSRI represents higher degree of importance.

From Table 5 we find that low job security was the most important factor behind the job dissatisfaction of female workers in 1983. Over the last 22 years, this factor did not lose its relative importance. In 2005, low job security remained the most important factor contributing to job dissatisfaction of female workers of different garments factory. This is because of the fact that in garments factories, there is no job security of any employee at all. Anybody may lose his or her job at any moment. According to motivation theories, when an employee believes that he or she can lose his or her job any moment without an acceptable reason, the employee loses his or her motivation to work and at the same time loses the “organizational citizenship”. His or her attitude toward the job then must be negative which in turn will lead to very low job satisfaction, *ceteris paribus*.

On the other hand, in 1983, the second most important factor contributing to job dissatisfaction of female workers was “low level of wages/salaries.” But in 2005, this factor was no longer a very important factor. According to respondents, the present study found that low level of wages/salaries was the fifth important factor out of eight factors that contribute to job dissatisfaction of female workers. However, “company policy and administration” was not an important factor that contributes to job dissatisfaction in 1983. But in 2005, “company policy and administration” was second important factor contributing to job dissatisfaction of female workers of garments factories. This finding suggest that despite the fact that readymade garment sector of Bangladesh has become more formal and professional management is being practiced in this sector, the relationship between the supervisors and the subordinate female workers have deteriorated for some unknown reason(s). It would be important to investigate the nature of management system being practiced in different readymade garments factories in Bangladesh. Such investigation will also help us know the reasons for very low job security.

Another important finding of the present study needs to be mentioned separately. In 1983, “absence of recognition” was not a very important factor that causes job dissatisfaction of female workers of garments factories. But over the last 22 years, the attitude of female workers about recognition has changed. They now find it an important factor determining job satisfaction. Thus absence of recognition was the third important factor that contributed to job dissatisfaction of female workers in 2005.

Since pay is the most important factor that contributes to job satisfaction of female workers, it is expected that there is a positive correlation between the level of pay and the level of overall job satisfaction. However, this present study did not find any significant difference of pay among different female workers. As a result, the nature of relationship between the level of pay and the level of job satisfaction could not be determined. Howbeit, Alam (1986) found that there was a positive correlation between the level of wages/salaries and overall job satisfaction status.

6. Limitations of the Study

It is quite possible that there is a relationship between job satisfaction status and age of the female workers. However, the present study did not analyze the possible relationship between job satisfaction status and age of female workers.

On the other hand, marital status of female workers may have some relationship with the overall job satisfaction status of female workers. But the present study did not try to find out if there is any relationship between marital status and job satisfaction status of female workers in different garments factories.

7. Conclusion

The study finds that in 2005, 28% of the female workers of different garments factories located in Dhaka City were more or less satisfied with their present jobs, the overall degree of satisfaction being 60% to 95%, while nobody was 100% satisfied (in reality 100% satisfaction level is not generally attainable). In 1983, 23% female workers were satisfied. Thus, we find that over the last

22 years, overall job satisfaction status of female workers of different garments factories did not change significantly, despite the fact that by the year 2005, most of the garments factories started to follow formal and professional management practices and needed to comply with a number of rules and regulations regarding workers' health and hygiene and other basic rights. However, in 2005, 52% female workers were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their present jobs, and 20% female workers were dissatisfied with their present jobs. In 1983, these percentages were 26% and 51%, respectively. These findings imply that over the last 22 years, the percentage of female workers dissatisfied with their jobs in different garments factories has decreased significantly. Now, about half of the female workers are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their present jobs. Thus we can conclude that over the last 22 years, the overall job satisfaction level of female workers in different garments factories have improved.

On the other hand, in 1983, "economic importance of the present job" was the most important factor that contributed to job satisfaction of female workers. However, in 2005, this factor was not considered a factor at all that contributes to job satisfaction. Instead, pay became the most important factor, which was not a factor at all in 1983. However, "absence of better alternative job" was second important factor that contributed to job satisfaction both in 1983 and 2005. This implies that if the female workers get better or similar jobs (similar in the sense of pay, job security, etc) outside the readymade garments sector, they will leave their present jobs at different garments factories and will take those alternative jobs.

Finally, in 1983, seven factors were contributing to job satisfaction of female workers, whereas in 2005, five factors are contributing to job satisfaction. "Possibility of growth" was no longer a factor in 2005 which was sixth important factor in 1983. In addition, "achievement" was not a factor in 2005 which was the seven most important factor in 1983.

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